

Physiographic Structure of Parner Tahsil: An Overview

Dr. Raghunath E. Najan

Head Department of Geography, New Arts, Commerce and Science College, Parner

Corresponding Author – Dr. Raghunath E. Najan

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.18874779

Introduction:

Physiographic structure mentions to the physical features and landform characteristics of any region i.e. relief, slope, altitude, drainage, geological formation, soil distribution etc. These features are the effect of long-term relations between endogenic forces such as volcanism, tectonic movements and exogenic forces such as weathering, erosion, and deposition etc.

The study of physiographic structure is a significant branch of physical geography, as it provides a basic framework for understanding the natural environment of any particular region. Physiographic situations play a pivotal role in determining climate, soil formation, drainage patterns, vegetation, agricultural practices, settlement distribution and economic activities.

Geographical studies also analysis of physiographic structure it helps in explaining spatial variations and the relationship between physical features and human activities. Therefore, a systematic study of physiographic structure is essential for land-use planning, resource management as well as sustainable regional development.

Location of Study Area:

Parner is located to the west of Ahmednagar city while the tahsil of the same name is located in the western part of Ahmednagar district. The Geographical location of tahsil is lies between $18^{\circ} 49'40''N$ to $19^{\circ}21'13''N$. Latitude and $74^{\circ} 10'22''E$ to

$74^{\circ}38'34''E$ Longitude. Physiographically, tahsil forms part of the Deccan Plateau, characterized by basaltic lava flows of volcanic origin.

Objectives of the Study Area:

The main objectives of this study are to understand the physiographical set up of the study area

Data Base and Methodology:

The present paper is based on primary and secondary data. Primary data have been collected through observation, organization of field surveys in study area. The use of different toposheets for analysis these are published by Survey of India.

Analysis and Discussion:

Topography of the study area:

Figure No. 1 Location Map of Parner tehsil

Physically the tahsil forms a part of Deccan Plateau in general and the Balaghat plateau in particular, to the east of the Sahyadri's. It occupies the western part of the Balaghat plateau also known as Ahmednagar Plateau, along with a narrow strip to the west of plateau rim occupied by the Kukadi river basin. It is the largest tahsil with a total area of 1930 sq. k.m. accounting for 11.32% of the district area.

The geographical situation of the tahsil is such that it is not far from the Pune (100 k.m.) and Mumbai (200 k.m.) metropolitan regions and Ahmednagar (40k.m.) city which provide market for agriculture and other products from the tahsil.

Figure No. 2 Digital Elevation Map

Physiographically, as mentioned earlier the tahsil occupies the north western part of the Balaghat or Ahmednagar plateau which itself is a part of Deccan plateau. It is the extension and widening of the Harishchandragad, then running eastwards and decreasing in height near Brahmanwada, takes a turn to the south-east and enters Parner tahsil in the form of plateau, which are completely traverses. The region is very irregular and hilly, consisting of the series of plateaus and table lands at various heights, the highest of them being the Kanhur-Plateau, formed by the widening out of the Harishchandragad range. Its average height is about 900 meters above MSL, though a few points rise to about 1000 meters. This plateau of Kanhur lies centrally over the range and to its north is the table land of

Vasunde that stretches as far north as the Mula river whose vally bottom is 100 meters below plateau rim. To the east of Parner town these are hills locally known as Kawadya Dongar and Dhawaladev Dongar which rise up to 958 meter above MSL and attain characteristics of a small mountain. The Dashabai Dongar ,5 k.m. to the north-north west of Parner town with 987 meter is the highest point in the tahsil to the south of the Parner town is a tract of hilly ground formed by spurs jutting out from the main range. The whole region seems to be highly dissected.

To the west the plateau rim slopes steeply and descends down to about 600 meters to the valley of the Ghod and its tributary, the kukadi. The western side of Kanhur plateau intra-trappean lime stone outcrops over many places. It is especially noticeable in the section of Wadgaon Darya, 5k.m.to the west of the Kanhur Pathar (plateau) village where the limestone cliffs worn by the falling water is decorated with beautiful “stalactites” and “stalagmites” in an underground cavern temple and a number of sinkholes higher up on the river bed, a rare feature at least on the Deccan Plateau. At Jategaon, further south, close of the Pune- Nagar highway is a smaller glen of the same kind.

Climatic Condition:

Climatically, Parner falls in the rain shadow zone of the Sahyadri's, the situation which hinders agricultural development in particular leading to overall under development. The climate of the tahsil is characterized by a hot summer and general dryness during major part of the year expect during south west monsoon season. The cold season in the tahsil commences from December and ends in the month of February. The period from March to the first week of June is the hot season. It is followed by the south –west monsoon season which lasts till

the end of September. October and November constitute the post-monsoon season.

Rainfall throughout the tahsil is very scanty, the annual average at Parner being as 574mm. It is always very erratic and uncertain leading to frequent crop failures and consequent droughts. Over three quarters of the annual rainfall is received within monsoon period with a long dry spell till the next monsoon, resulting in to scarcity of even drinking water.

The temperature is low in winter which is experienced from middle of November to the end of February. December is the coldest month of the year. The cold waves associated with westerly disturbance are frequently experienced causing drops of minimum temperature. From March to the break of monsoon the day temperatures increased progressively, the night remaining comparatively cool. With the onset of monsoon in the tahsil there is appreciable drop in temperature and weather becomes pleasant.

Drainage System:

The drainage of the Parner tahsil belongs to two major river system of Maharashtra, the Godawari to the north and the Bhima to the south, though only minor tributaries of both of them drain the area of the tahsil, the centre line of the plateau roughly forming water shed between the two rivers.

The Mandohal odha (stream) alongwith the Kanhur odha drains the north western part of the plateau towards the Mula to the north. The Kalu Nadi perhaps the largest of the streams from Parner tahsil, rises along the northern slopes on center upland or Mal on the plateau, little north of Parner town and drains central north of the tahsil to the Mula. Further east is the Karpari Nadi which drains the north eastern tahsil right from the karandi and Diksal villages located about 5 to 6 k.m. north and north-east of Parner.

Alkuti Nala, Padal Nala and Siddheshwarwadi Nala rising along the western slopes close to Kanhur and Parner township, alongwith other minor streams drain the western part of the tahsil to the Kukady Nadi, a tributary of the Ghod. The Dudh Nadi, the Bhairoba Nala, the Jambhal Nala, the Kadus Nala along with other with minor streams drain the southern part of the tahsil to the Ghod which itself is a tributary of the Bhima.

The Hanga Nadi originating along slopes all around Parner township, drains eastern and south eastern part of the tahsil to the Ghod, the confluence being out of the tahsil to the south east. The Sina River, the main river of the Balaghat Plateau, rises along slopes of Kavdya Dongar and in the vicinity of Jamgaon and drains a smaller eastern part of the tahsil.

The features carved out by the various rivers and streams are not very conspicuous barring few examples. The Mula flowing along the northern boundary flows through a narrow and deep valley with a zigzag course. The Kukadi flowing along the south western boundary has formed the famous “Potholes” in its bed, which present a picturesque view of the area. Geographers all over Maharashtra come to visit these “Potholes” located near the Nighoj village as well as the “Limestone” cavern with “stalactite” and “stalagmite” formations at Wadgaon Darya village located 18 km. north west of parner town.

Soil Variation:

Soils over the plateau in many parts of Parner tahsil are not very deep but suited for a number of rabbi crops. However, on the terraces the soils are very much inferior and the hill slopes are stony and poorer. A barren tract is noticed to the north of a line drawn east to west through Takali Dhokeshwar, about 15 km north of Parner, and as for north as the slopes down to the Mula,

which is of great extent and is mostly un-arable being little better than bare basalt, unfit for anything except sheep grazing. Fairly productive black soils are seen only in a narrow strip along the kukadi and the Ghod. Over the entire plateau of the tahsil very small sections are under poor grade forests, some of them very recently planted, and proportion of area under barren and uncultivable wastes is fairly larger.

Conclusion:

The physiographic structure of Parner Tahsil is dominated by the basaltic Deccan Plateau, with undulating terrain, seasonal drainage pattern and fertile black soils. These

physical features strongly impact on land use pattern, agricultural development, settlement patterns, water availability in the region.

References:

1. Socio-Economic Abstract Ahilyanagar
2. Census Handbook Ahilyanagar
3. Survey of India's Toposheet
4. A Geospatial Approach to Enhance Point of the Interest and Tourism Potential Centers in
5. Parner Tehsil in Maharashtra, India, Vasudev S. Salunke et al Int J Sci Res Sci Eng Technol January-February-2021; 8 (1): 186-196